

The Portrayal Of Babur In The Eyes Of Fritz Wuertle

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Abstract: *the adventure novel “The Prince of Andijan” by F. Wurtle features several unique depictions aimed at providing an objective and accurate representation of the events described in “Baburnoma” particularly the image of Babur. Babur’s portrayal, adorned with Islamic faith, national spirit, and a heroic nature, is explained by the fact that the author, despite being of a different nationality, integrates divine and Quranic teachings and concepts.*

Keywords — adventure novel, historical and artistic accuracy, character, artistic interpretation, composition, style, artistic skill.

INTRODUCTION.

More than half a century has passed since the publication of the short story “Babur – Tiger” by the German-Austrian scientist and writer Fries Wuertle. In 2011, the work was translated into Uzbek by Yanglish Egamova and titled “Prince of Andijan.” The poet S. Sayyid, who wrote the foreword for the translation, provides the following information: “*Fries Wuertle wrote this work for young people under the influence of ‘Baburnoma.’*” The book was originally published in Australia in 1947” (emphasis ours, O.X.). In European literature, there has been a tradition since the Renaissance of educating young people about the great leaders and scholars of the East. Artistic works about figures such as Genghis Khan, Amir Timur, Ibn Rushd, Ibn Sina, and Omar Khayyam have served this purpose for the European cultural and artistic community. The story “Prince of Andijan” was written with this goal in mind. The author of the foreword recognized and accurately documented this intention.

The compositional structure of the short story is distinctive. It is composed of small chapters with titles similar to those in A. Qadiri’s novels “O’tkan Kunlar” (“Bygone days”) and “Mehrobdan Chayon” (“Scorpion from the Altar”). This tradition is also present in Western literature in the works of authors like J. Boccaccio, M. de Cervantes, J. Swift, and C. Dickens. In this case, the composition is organized by chapter headings, with each sub-heading reflecting the content of its respective sub-chapter. This structure facilitates the reader’s transition from one story or plot to another. In our view, the adventurous nature of the work necessitated such a compositional design. These headings are crucial for readers who eagerly and carefully follow every step of the hero at the center of the adventure.

The work “Prince of Andijan” is composed of 19 short chapters, including “Osmondagi Temir qoziq” (“Cynosure star in the Sky”), “Karvonboshi”, (“Caravan Head”) “Jazolash” (“Punishment”), and “Umarshayx Mirzoning

o’limi” (“Death of Umarsheikh Mirza’) A key aspect is the strong artistic cohesion between these sections. Each event under one heading seamlessly connects to the next. The titles of the short stories are not merely formal; each one conveys a distinct artistic concept.

Although the writer presents the work as an adventure story, its internal content and logic remain faithful to historical facts—the logic of “Baburnoma.” The author creates a clear portrayal of Babur’s personality based on “Baburnoma” and strives to depict events and characters objectively. This aspect is evident in the following ways:

1. F. Wurtle deeply understood Babur’s strong faith in God, which he conveyed through the character’s thoughts, needs, desires, and decisions.
2. The author profoundly grasped the spirit of Babur’s time and place. He accurately depicted the unwritten morals and rules of the military society. Babur and his entourage are essentially warriors, and this is vividly shown through their interactions, thoughts, actions, interests, and goals. In a word, he effectively illustrated that they are deeply influenced by the fighting environment. He demonstrated that everyone in this society, from the king to the minister, the vizier, the scientist, the poet, the farmer, the moneylender, the merchant, and the teacher, are military men whose blood is stirred by the battle drum.
3. In the story, Babur and his environment are shaped by a series of violent actions. This intensity is reflected in their lively communication. F. Wuertle studied this aspect deeply, and the translator successfully conveyed the rhythm of the warriors’ dialogue typical of the military society.

The story begins with a dialogue between the young Babur and his teacher, Mirza Ullah. At the outset, the writer introduces a symbolic image of a pomegranate tree growing along the caravan route. This ancient pomegranate tree

transcends nationality, culture, language, and skin color, offering shade and fruit to anyone weary and thirsty from the desert. This symbolizes the youthful generosity of Babur's descendants and Eastern scholars. The conversation between Babur and his teacher revolves around human perfection, faith, and science. The Cynosure star mentioned during this dialogue also takes on a symbolic meaning, residing in the protagonist's heart as a representation of Babur's dreams and aspirations throughout the story.

Mirza Ullah reprimands Babur for not following his instructions. Interestingly, this method of punishment is perceived negatively by neither Babur nor the onlookers. Everyone believes in the principle that justice is impartial, even for the king, and they live by it. During the punishment, the main concern is how the young prince will react. Will he cry and resist, or will he face the pain courageously? Naturally, Babur endures the punishment bravely, without shedding a single tear or showing weakness.

The author likely included this episode at the beginning to build trust and admiration for Babur among European readers. Additionally, it hints at the severe challenges Babur will face in the future.

Following this episode, Babur's life takes a violent turn. News soon arrives of Umarshaikh's death, and the young Babur is crowned.

F. Würtle vividly described the Akhsi fortress, the dovecote, and the death of Umarshaikh that occurred there. *"Kechagina podshohimiz hamishagidek kaptarlarni ko'rish uchun tag'in tepaga, Axsidagi eng baland minoraning sakkiz yuz to'qson uchta zinasi bo'ylab chiqdi. U yerda uzoq, ancha uzoq qolib ketdi..."*

Men aytganimdek, agar Axsining eng baland minorasi tepasidagi eng yuqori maydonchasidan turib tosh otilsa, uning suvga shaloplab tushganini eshitgunga qadar Allohga uch bora shukrona aytib, shaytonni olti marta la'natlashga ulgurish mumkin. Ishonamizki, Umarshayx Mirzo ham qullagan paytda dahshat ichida yerga yetib borgunicha Allohga shukrona aytib, shaytonni la'natlashga o'zida kuch topa olgan (Yesterday, our king, as usual, climbed the eight hundred and ninety-three steps of the highest tower in Akhsi to the top to see the pigeons. He stayed there for a very long time... As mentioned, if a stone were thrown from the highest platform atop Akhsi's tallest minaret, one could praise God three times and curse Satan six times before hearing it splash into the water. We imagine that during his descent, Umarshaikh Mirza thanked God and mustered the strength to curse the devil until he landed on the ground in horror)".

The portrayal's uniqueness lies in enabling readers to fully grasp the towering height and majestic presence of the Akhsi minaret, as well as the physical and mental strength, bravery, and faith of Umarshaikh Mirza. In reality, someone who falls accidentally typically screams, experiences fear, and panics, calling for help from those nearby. The author draws an extraordinary conclusion from the love and tragic circumstances of this location. Umarshaikh expresses his unwavering trust in Mirza's perfect faith and his reliance on

God even in the most precarious situations. This allows us to objectively envision the mindset of Umarshaikh Mirza, who assumes the role of an episodic hero in the narrative, within the Islamic environment in which he lived.

Details surrounding Umarshaikh's death are absent in "Baburnoma". The text merely states: "He fell from the dovecote and died." The opening sentence of "Baburnoma" reads: *"Tengri taaloning inoyati va hazrati on Sarvari koinotning shafoti bilan va chahoryori bosafolarning himmati birlan seshanba kuni ramazon oyining beshida tarix sekkiz yuz to'qson to'qquzda Farg'ona viloyatida o'n ikki yoshda podshoh bo'ldum (By the grace of Almighty God and the intercession of our Prophet, and through the efforts of the four caliphs, on Tuesday, the fifth day of Ramadan, in the year eight hundred and ninety-nine, at the age of twelve, I became king in the province of Fergana.)"* However, F. Würtle employs artistic imagination to depict events preceding and following this incident. Kasimbek, one of Babur's intimate advisors, also assumes a fantastical persona. S. Sayyid underscores this in his preface, noting: "Certainly, F. Würtle as an author has every right to employ various artistic techniques and styles, including artistic texture. In this regard, Kasimbek, who was thirty years old when young Babur ascended the throne, is portrayed as a wise man with weak eyes and profound wisdom."

In our view, the death of Umarshaikh Mirza and the artistic portrayal of Kasimbek in elaborate attire are not coincidental but are linked to the author's artistic intention. It appears that the author introduced Kasimbek's character in the narrative to elucidate his conjectures about Umarshaikh's death. Drawing from "Baburnama" the author gleaned insights into Kasimbek's loyalty, paternal closeness to Babur, and bravery in challenging circumstances. Dressing him as a sage and wise advisor was essential for advancing the storyline effectively.

In a way, Kasimbek's character serves as a detective within the story. As Navoi once remarked about Ahmad Yugnaki, "Though his outward eyes were closed, his inner vision was exceptionally sharp." Through this insight, Umarshaikh's treacherous schemes are uncovered, and his plots against Babur are thwarted. Kasimbek's actions ensure that Babur's youthful aspirations, inspired by his teacher's narratives, come to fruition successfully.

The second strange character in the work is the character of Babur's grandfather, thief friend Khoji. This image is also a product of the writer's artistic imagination, and it seems that the image of a friend in European knight novels is based on it. Most of the characters of "friends" who were met by chance in Knight's novels are street children with no family history. Logically, they are more risk-averse because they have nothing to lose. It is for this reason that they excel in loyalty to their patrons or friends. Khoji is one of those characters. He treats Babur as his equal friend. He does not return from his previous habits, for example, stealing. He says what he thinks and does what he wants. He is guided by chance, not logic. Babur's arch surrounded by these features differed from the state. He deserves the love of Babur and the hatred of the whites. But in the attack on the fortress of Akhsi, Khoji accidentally became

the cause of Babur's victory. Umar Sheikh holds the Beg of Akhsi Castle, who betrayed Mirza. He puts it in a chest and presents it to Babur as a gift. What kind of gift is this from Babur? answers the question as follows:

- *Kechiring,-javob berdi Xoji, ulug' a'yonlardek ta'zim qilarkan,-qachondan beri podshoh biror ko'cha bolasidan qimmatbaho sovg'a olibdi? Sizga keltirganimiz iflos, arzimas sovg'a. Ammo uni iltifot bilan qabul qiling, do'stingiz Xojining sizga bo'lgan sadoqati belgisi(I beg your pardon," Khoji replied, bowing reverently like a revered saint, "since when does a king accept a lavish gift from a street urchin? What we present to you is a humble, insignificant gift. Nevertheless, accept it as a token of your friend Haji's unwavering loyalty to you).*

The work also features several characters like Mirza Ullah, Hasan Karvan, Jallod, and six Bahadir. However, each of them fully unveils their traits only in specific episodes related to Babur. Mirza Ullah's blend of indolence and wisdom, Hasan Karvan's mix of brusqueness and intelligence, Jallod's recklessness and cruelty, and Six Bahadir's loyalty and bravery—all these aspects serve to illuminate Babur's character and deeds.

The most compelling figure in the narrative is Babur, portrayed with a deep and dynamic character. Initially depicted as a scholar thirsty for knowledge, he evolves into a passionate dreamer with a large heart. At times, he exhibits the playfulness and stubbornness of a child. Following his father's death, he transforms into a bold and wise entrepreneur and leader. These facets are vividly showcased during the ceremony of his ascension as Khan on white felt, where Shah Babur surprises everyone with his decisive actions.

The author incorporates the story of the rabbit to emphasize Babur's characteristic leadership. Before the assault on Ashki, a severe sandstorm ensnares the army, leaving their food and weapons convoy stranded behind. Amidst hesitation and confusion within the army about his whereabouts, young Babur ventures out alone to locate the caravan. This act sparks gossip and mistrust among the soldiers, symbolized by replacing the cock's tail on their flags with women's nipples—an act that traitors in Ashki misinterpret. However, Babur successfully retrieves the vital caravan, dispelling rumors and restoring trust.

Most importantly, Babur emerges as a just and devout servant of God, loyal to his friends, ruthless to his enemies, wise among scholars, and brave in battle. F. Wurtle's interpretation portrays Babur as modest and uninterested in fame. Even after the conquest of Akhsi fortress, he attributes success to collective effort, stating, "This is not my achievement; it belongs to all of us." When honored by his soldiers, he responds with the following words:

- *Men Andijondagi shohlar tepaligida ota-bobolarimizdan qolgan oq kigizga o'tirganimga hali ko'p vaqt bo'lgani yo'q. Mening rutbanning belgisini o'n ikkita kuchli qo'l, jangchilarim ushlab turdi, shu qo'llardan olitiasi jangda halok bo'ldi. Ko'plab boshqa yigitlarimiz bilan birga, tag'in uchta qahramon ajal so'qmog'i orqali jannat bog'lariga ravona*

bo'lishdi. Ular u yerda chodirlarini tikishdi, mening otam, shoh Umarshayx Mirzo ham ularning yonida... Alloh mehribon, u ularga jannatda otlarni minib, quvnoq o'yinlar bilan mashg'ul bo'lishlari uchun qurollarini qaytarib bersa kerak (Not long ago, I sat upon the ancient white felt left by our ancestors on the hill of kings in Andijan. The insignia of my rank was upheld by twelve strong hands—my warriors, six of whom fell in battle. Alongside many other young men, three additional heroes walked the path of death to the gardens of paradise, where they pitched their tents. My father, Shah Umarshaikh Mirza, also rests there among them... God is merciful; He will return their weapons so they may ride horses and enjoy joyous games in heaven.)

Babur is portrayed as a devout Muslim who adheres to the teachings of the Quran and the Prophet Muhammad in navigating through various complex situations. For instance, when Qalabegi boasted about being a magician and astrologer, Babur responded in a manner consistent with his beliefs:

- *Olamni yaratgan Alloh,-dedi Bobur,-ertalab quyoshni sharq tomondan chiqaradi. Asxi qal'abegi, gapingga qaraganda, yulduzlar sening imoyingga bo'yinsunisharkan. Sendan talabim: quyoshni g'arb tomondan chiqar...(God, the Creator of the world," Babur declared, "raises the sun in the morning from the east." To Akhsi's castle, he added, "According to your claim, the stars obey your command. I challenge you: make the sun rise from the west.")*

The dialogue between Babur and Akhsi's castle echoes the historical debate between Abraham and Pharaoh in Islamic history.

It's worth noting that the author has made several errors concerning royal etiquette, specific details, and the use of religious terminology: firstly, the depiction of young Babur being declared king after Umarshaikh Mirza's death, expecting the entire state, army, and people to kneel before him (p. 26), reflects Western monarchical customs rather than Eastern kingdom etiquette; secondly, describing the royal bow made of mammoth bone that Babur shot while standing on white felt (p. 35) does not align with Timurid dynasty traditions; thirdly, on page 50, Babur's teacher Mirza Ullah is depicted praying the morning prayer after sunrise, whereas it is typically performed before sunrise in Islamic practice. Such inaccuracies and interpretations can be found in various historical works, yet it's beneficial for young, non-specialist readers to be aware of them.

Overall, F. Wurtle's adventure story "The Prince of Andijan" presents several distinctive portrayals aimed at a fair and truthful interpretation of events from "Baburnama", particularly, Babur's character adorned with Islamic faith, national spirit, and heroic nature. Despite being of a different nationality, the author's depiction of Babur is rooted in divine and Quranic teachings and concepts. This portrayal makes Babur's character compelling and complete, appealing to readers as an idealized figure.

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